

**INTERESTS OF PREGNANCY FOLLOW-UP IN COWS
AFTER EMBRYO TRANSFER:
SPECIAL FOCUSING ON IVP & NT**

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Introduction

Embryonic development of mammals fertilized eggs go among others through one segmentation step which is the first one leading to the formation of a pluricellular organism. This segmentation consists of numerous mitotic divisions of the egg cells, which finally generate a morula, constituted of large number of blastomers. These blastomers are segregated in two populations: the first one, internal mass cell, represents the future embryo with some of his annexes; the second one constitutes the trophoblast which will give chorion epithelium.

Some characteristics of ruminants implantation are described such as:

- a relatively late occurring implantation (35th day),
- an embryonic diapause described in some ruminants species,
- no great influence of LH or PRL secretion on luteal function. Indeed, in early pregnant females, the mechanism described to avoid corpus luteum regression is more an inhibition of luteolysis than a luteotropic phenomenon,
- the 16-25 days old conceptus produces an antiluteolytic substance identified as trophoblastin or bTP1. This protein was classified as a member of interferon tau family (Imakawa et al., 1987).

In all species of placental mammals, progesterone is required for implantation, embryonic development and for the normal course of gestation. Initially, the corpus luteum is the only source of progesterone and it remains the main producer during a more or less long time of gestation depending on the species (ovine 50 days; bovine 200 days). Corpus luteum maintenance hangs on the trophoblastic secretion of trophoblastic protein on day 17 in the bovine (bTP). This leads to a prolongation of the oestrous cycle which is the first sign of the establishment of a pregnancy. This clinical sign can be confirmed on day 21, 22 by blood progesterone assay (day 21 from 2 to 8 ng/ml).

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Different methods exist which permit to confirm pregnancy and to follow the female along its gestation.

During the long preimplantation period (20 days in the bovine), trophoblastic tissue differentiates and starts to synthesize on day 16 to the end of gestation a family of specific proteins which are known as PSPB and bPAG. Buttler et al. (1982) purified the PSPB by precipitation and chromatography and showed it to be a glycoprotein with a molecular weight of about 50.000 daltons and an isoelectric point of between 4 and 4.4. Sasser et al. (1987) demonstrated that the PSPB protein was detectable in the blood of pregnant cows by radioimmunoassay and showed that the serum levels increased gradually and then suddenly just before term from 1.2 ± 0.34 ng/ml on day 29, the levels increased to 9.3 ng/ml on day 91, 35.4 ± 5.6 ng on day 185, 149.8 ng/ml on day 269 and suddenly increased 2 days before parturition to 541 ± 144 ng/ml. This peak just before parturition is no doubt related to the physiological changes occurring at this time preparing or accompanying delivery.

Of course, this protein is not found in the serum of non pregnant heifers. However, Zoli et al. (1990) described accessory source of bPAG in bull testis and in heifer ovary. Detected from the start of gestation, PSPB and bPAG represent reliable markers of gestation and their radio-immunoassays provide methods of diagnosis with an accuracy higher than 95%. Nevertheless, special care must be given to the very long half-life of this family of glycoprotein which leads to a possible wrong test if an assay is performed during the 100 days following parturition. Fortunately, embryo recipients are generally heifers of cows that have calved more than 80 days before. bPAG or PSPB follow-up during pregnancy permit to keep track of the vitality of the foeto-placental unit. Till now, due to the large individual variations in maternal level of pregnancy proteins, only the decrease or disappearance of these proteins, indicating a possible embryonic or fetal death, can lead to a clinical diagnosis of pregnancy interruption. In the other hand, the increased concentrations can be related to breed differences between recipient and embryo, or to the presence of large quantity of trophoblastic tissue. This can reflect the presence of a multiple pregnancy or an hypertrophy of trophoblastic tissue; the last part of this presentation will focus on this process in cow and give some hypothetical explanations.

Since the 28th day of pregnancy, the ultrasonography permits a direct examination of the embryo or foetus and of the present fluid. However, after the 90-100st day of gestation, the increasing distance between the probe and the foetus does not permit a correct examination.

Rectal palpation and examination of uterus and ovaries is certainly the most common method of pregnancy detection and confirmation in cow. Various criteria are observable along the pregnancy as described in table 1. Insertion of the hand in the rectum permits to palpate the pelvic floor in search of the hard firm structure of the cervix. A caudal traction exerted on the cervix and the ventral intercornual ligament allows the hand to examine the uterine body, horns symmetry and size and the ovaries in the pelvic cavity. Early pregnancy diagnosis can so be made quite accurately in heifers and cows, respectively from 30 and 35 days post-insemination, and hangs on the statement of characteristic signs of gestation such as palpation of enlarged uterine horn with placental fluids (and special care to manipulation of embryonic vesicle because of its low resistance to excessive pressure). In the same way, placement of thumb and fingers around the gravid horn followed by slow forwards and backwards displacements permits the tense spherical form to slip between them.

From 40 days, the gravid uterine horn is more extended while the uterine wall becomes slightly thinner. The mobilisation of this horn by the hand accompanied by a gentle compression reveals the fetal membranes, before the uterine wall escapes. This "membrane slip" technique can be used for

differential diagnosis between pregnancy and others fluids causing uterine distention such as hydramnios, pyometritis...

Table 1. Informations furnished by rectal palpation.

Month of gestation	Informations obtained by examination of the:	
	UTERUS	OVARIES
1	Amniotic sac: diam= 2cm length= 18cm	Corpus Luteum
2	Foetal length: 6-8cm Unsymmetrical horns Subtil palpation of foetal membranes	Persistant Corpus Luteum on ipsi lateral and same ovary
3	Total dissymetry Foetal length: 15 cm 300 to 700 ml of liquid Positive succussion	Persistant Corpus Luteum on ipsi lateral and same ovary
4	Foetal length 25-35 cm Uterin thrill Possible palpation of cotyledons Clear horns' dissymetry	Persistant Corpus Luteum on ipsi lateral and same ovary
5	Uterus in abdominal cavity, no more totally palpable Thrill and cotyledons	Persistant Corpus Luteum on ipsilateral and same ovary
6	The members and the head are Located in front of the anterior side of the pubis	Persistant Corpus Luteum on ipsi lateral and same ovary

Is the pregnancy success related to the embryo origin ?
Our experience in nuclear transfer

Some reports have mentioned the occurrence of pregnancy alterations associated with embryo transfer (Wilson et al., 1995), in vitro development (Walker et al., 1992 a,b; Wilson et al., 1995) and nuclear transfer (Willadsen et al., 1991; Seidel, 1992; Bondioli, 1992; Wilson et al., 1995; Walker et al., 1996; Ectors et al., 1996), such as increased gestation lengths and birth weights. Wilson et al. (1995) have well demonstrated that birth weight and variance of birth weight were greater for nuclear transfer calves than for embryo transfer and greater for embryo transfer ones than for natural mating. Previously, Walker et al. (1992 a, b) have reported the incidence of increased mean gestation length and mean birth weight of lambs when the embryos were cultured in vitro for 3 or 5 days. This increase in utero growth was transient and a weight normalization was observed during the first year of life. Because of the apparition of such pregnancy alterations, even with embryos obtained ex-vivo

and manipulated a short time in vitro, the follow-up of pregnancy using non-invasive investigation method such as blood sampling is of clinical and research interest. On the clinical point of view, the monitoring of P4, bPAG or PSPB may help to detect earlier placental abnormalities and embryonic or foetal mortality.

After ex-vivo embryo transfer, the occurrence of embryo defect is very low, close to those obtained after natural mating or artificial insemination. The appearance of increased gestation lengths and birth weights is clearly demonstrated with gestation issued from IVF embryo transfer, and more important again after nuclear transfer.

Table 2 presents the mean values of bPAG in single pregnancies following transfer of two NT blastocysts (5 cows). Because of the low effective of pregnancies obtained after cycle 1 and 2 NT, mean concentrations of bPAG were pooled. These bPAG levels were in agreement with those observed in our laboratory after IVF or artificial insemination (Zoli et al., 1992). In those cases, mean concentrations of bPAG observed during peripartal weeks were around 1600 to 5000 ng/ml.

In table 3, four cases of pathologies among the pregnant heifers are presented. Cow #7115 received two first cycle NT blastocysts. Her bPAG profile was typical of that observed in a pregnancy with early abortion. At about week 7 to 8 there was a rapid decline in bPAG, presumably reflecting loss of the conceptus. bPAG values were not recorded for cow #276 before day 158. At this time, her bPAG values were decreasing, again indicating the likelihood of fetal death. Death was confirmed by expulsion of a mummified foetus after a PgF2 α injection. The cow #270 was carrying a second cycle NT singleton (diagnosed after 90 d of gestation by palpation per rectum). Note the sharp increase of her bPAG concentrations during the two last weeks of pregnancy. The heifer #8527 was carrying second cycle NT twins (diagnosed after 90 days of gestation by palpation per rectum). Her bPAG values were in agreement with the presence of two foetuses. Note a temporary decrease of her bPAG values between weeks 32 to 39 and the subsequent marked increase during the two last weeks of pregnancy. After delivery, the placenta of one of the newborns (Decima) showed an unusual morphology, with a region resembling that of a hydatiform mole.

Table 2. Mean $\pm$ SEM concentrations (ng/ml) of bPAG in singleton pregnancies following transfer of IVF or cloned embryos (two embryos transferred in recipient)

Weeks after ET	IVF embryos mean $\pm$ SEM ng/ml	Cloned embryos mean $\pm$ SEM ng/ml
5	3 $\pm$ 0.5	1.6 $\pm$ 0.3
6		1.6 $\pm$ 0.4
8		4.5 $\pm$ 0.3
12	21 $\pm$ 2.6	9.9 $\pm$ 2.9
26	73 $\pm$ 16	79.0 $\pm$ 12
29	108 $\pm$ 28	119.0 $\pm$ 29
32	148 $\pm$ 33	204.0 $\pm$ 51
35	137 $\pm$ 28	252.0 $\pm$ 60
36	168 $\pm$ 40	248.0 $\pm$ 59
Peripartal week	1602 $\pm$ 559	5022.0 $\pm$ 1789

The weights of first cycle nuclear transfer newborns were normal (mean: 38.6 Kg). However, weights of second cycle nuclear transfer newborns were higher (mean: 55.0 Kg). Nevertheless, these weights are not uncommon for calves of the Belgian Blue strain (mean $\pm$ SEM: 40.7 $\pm$ 5.2 Kg).

None of the calves presented any morphological abnormalities and the karyotype of each of them was strictly normal. Nevertheless, we have observed some placental abnormalities. One of them (Zapatta) presented umbilical cord and placental (20 Kg) oedema associated with foetal oedema and hydramnios, although recovery of calf was rapid (2 days). Another (Decima, recipient cow #8527) had placental hypertrophy, with an increase in the number and diameter of cotyledons (200 cotyledons of 20 cm diameter). This placenta was the one with the hydatiform mole, which was probably responsible for the bPAG increase observed at the end of pregnancy. Presently, we have no explanation for the apparent abnormal placental development noted in some of the second cycle nuclear transfer calves. However, what is clear is that the majority of calves were of normal size despite the extensive micromanipulations carried out in producing these embryos.

Table 3. Levels of bPAG during abnormal pregnancies of four cows following transfers of two NT embryos.

Weeks after ET	bPAG concentrations (ng/ml)			
	#7115	#276	#270	#8527
6	1.2	/	1.1	2.0
7	3.7	/	1.1	
8	2.9	/	4.9	6.9
12	0.4	/	8.6	18
14	<0.2	/	12	/
20		/	31.9	92.5
24		40.5	/	/
26		38.9	/	/
28		/	105.0	456.0
29		13.9	/	730.0
31		2.1	200.0	
32		0.5	/	630.0
35		<0.2	397.0	425.0
36		/	375.0	360.0
37		/	492.0	348.0
38		/	689.0	373.0
39		Mummified	2095.0	3400.0
40		foetus	9133.0	12350.0
		male	female	
		calf	calves	

Table 4. Characteristics of the calves obtained after the nuclear transfer procedure (Cycles 1 and 2 nuclear transfers)

Calf name	A	B	C	D	E
First cycle nuclear transfer					
Mannitol 3204	2M (I+II)	+7	40	M	
Zappatta	1579	2Bl (II+III)	+6	35	M
Rouge 1402	1Bl (II to III)		+13	40	M
Noir 6827	2Bl (I+I)	+6	40	M	
Laurel*	7165	2Bl (II+II)	-7	30	M
Hardy*	"	"	"	30	M
Castafiore	6203	2Bl (II+III)	+16	45	F
			Mean $\pm$ SEM=		
			37.1 $\pm$ 2.1		
Second cycle nuclear transfer					
Dupond ^o	8529	2Bl (II+II)	+12	70	M
Dupont ^o	270	2M (II+II)	+11	70	M
Nana ^o	7115	2Bl	+2	55	F
Decima*/ ^o	8527	2Bl	+2	45	F
Martha*/ ^o	8527	2Bl	+2	35	F
			Mean $\pm$ SEM=		
			55.0 $\pm$ 6.9		

A: recipient Nr. B: N^o, type and classes of transferred embryos; Bl=blastocyste, M=morula; C: deviation (days) in comparison with a mean pregnancy length of 281 days. D: newborns weights (Kg). E: sex of the calves. *:twins issued from one recipient. ^o:twins issued from two different recipients.

These experiments combining transfers of cloned embryos and pregnancies follow-up by bPAG plasmatic determinations show some abnormal profiles. First, in cows numbered 7115 and 276, bPAG were decreasing in relation with an early embryonic resorption (#7115) or a late fetal death (#276) (see Table 2). These abortions may be in relation with the low rate of implantation observed after transfer of cloning embryos (Ectors et al., 1995). Secondly, increased levels of bPAG during the two last weeks of gestation were observed in animals #270 and #8527 (see Table 3). It may be possible that these bPAG perturbations are in relation with the breed differences between the foetus and the mother as described by Guilbault et al. (1990). This antigenic dissimilarity has been related to larger placentas in mice (James, 1967) and higher calf birth weights in cows (Ounsted, 1978).

Through the transfer of cloned embryos and follow-up of pregnancies, our data suggested that these manipulations may be responsible of a complex syndrome associating large calf (at birth), trophoblastic hypertrophy and abnormal profiles of bPAG. Such observations were already described by several authors. Milk production, calving ease and days open (Adkinson et al., 1977; Hayes et al., 1985; Moya et al., 1989; Saner et Gaillard, 1988) as well as gestation length and calf birth weight (Guilbault et al., 1985) are affected by the genotype of the foetus. King et al. (1985 a,b) showed also, through the use of embryo transfer, that gestation length and calf birth weight are affected when the breeds of the transferred embryo and that of the recipient are different. Using endocrine follow-up

during pre-partum, Guilbault et al. (1990) and Zoli et al. (1992) confirmed these observations and pointed out the effect of the distance between breeds of recipient and that of the transferred embryo. In a study developed parallelly in porcine, ovine and bovine species, Walker et al. (1992) observed a reduction of embryo vitality after transfer, higher rates of foetal and perinatal mortality and abnormally high birth weights. These authors suggested that these observations are related to inappropriate activation of the embryonic genome induced by deficiencies or excesses in the culture medium. More recently, Wilson et al. (1995) in a large study involving natural mating, artificial insemination, embryo transfer and nuclear transfer showed that birth weight and variance of birth weight were greater for nuclear transfer calves than for embryo transfer and greater for embryo transfer than for natural mating. They observed also that this increased variability in terms of birth weight disappear during the first year after birth. Because their nuclear transfer embryos were developed in sheep oviducts, these authors in contradiction with Walker et al. (1992), attributed this accelerated fetal growth to developmental alterations resulting from the cloning procedure.

Our study combined breeds differences between embryo and recipient, in vitro production of donor embryo for cloning, in vitro maturation of recipient oocyte, one or two cycles nuclear transfer and in vitro development of reconstituted embryos in co-culture with bovine oviductal epithelial cells (Ectors et al., 1993; 1995). Cumulative informations recorded - in vitro and in vivo embryonic mortality, bPAG concentrations follow-up, placental, umbilical cord and newborn examinations - showed that most alterations are mainly localized in the trophoblastic compartment. In our experiment, high birth weights are probably a consequence of a placental hypertrophy starting early in pregnancy as revealed by high bPAG levels throughout pregnancy. Our experimental conditions as well as our observations do not permit to point out one single hypothetical cause explaining this syndrome. We postulate the source of these placental alterations as originating from breed difference and/or in vitro fertilization of not fully competent oocytes and/or in vitro presence of gametes and embryos and/or cloning procedure. In the present situation, one explanation could be given such as these placental alterations may be a result of a perturbation in gene expression involving methylation pattern of DNA. Gene expression during early embryonic development is controlled in a very precise manner, and slight deviations from the norm may interfere with development (Westhusin et al., 1995). Previous researches in mice have shown that abnormal expression of genes coding for growth factors during embryonic development can have dramatic effects on birth weights of offspring (IGF-II, DeChiara et al., 1990).

Conclusions

In this report, pregnancies were obtained after extreme in vitro conditions- IVM/F/C of the donor embryos, - IVM, enucleation and artificial activation of the recipient oocytes, - nuclear transfer and - IVC of the reconstituted embryos. Even if the incidence of this syndrome is relatively low after embryo transfer, a possible increasing of its occurrence cannot be excluded in correlation with an incomplete maturation of oocytes at the time of fertilization, smaller follicles giving non competent or partially competent oocytes. An other explanation of this syndrome resulting in the higher variation in newborn calves weight may be also partly explained by the in vitro conditions. The gametes and/or embryos may be submitted to media containing embryotoxic substances. In the other hand, gametes and/or embryos may not found embryotropic substances in the media like growth factors...

Owing to this phenomenon, strict recommendations should be followed concerning rigorous follow-up of pregnancies obtained after transfer of IVM/IVF/IVC or cloned embryos by pregnancy proteins (PSPB, PAG...) or hormone (placental lactogen, estrone sulfate) assay and, after birth, macroscopic examinations of newborn, cord and caruncles.

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